

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.44 Max: 63.76	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1217 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
	In cross-section? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No			In elevation drawing? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		

DEFINITION <i>retaining wall in room 4</i>	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1208	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	<i>height (robbing)</i>
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1016, 1208, 1113, 1113	Covers: 1001
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: *Retaining wall stretching West-East. Its eastern part has been robbed -> Elevation almost not visible on this eastern part. Light slope from West to East (up)*

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: *North of Area B, Northern wall of room 4 and 5*
Shape: *Linear, stretching West-East.*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:	<i>Detailed sketch of eastern part of wall 1217</i>

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: West - East

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)
visible

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify) + 1 shard pottery
Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) 3x12 Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz
cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: 9,50m
L. $\approx$ 585 cm / W $\approx$ 47 cm / h $\approx$ 30 cm

Description:

West 368 cm length of $\approx$ 60 cm high -
East + 217 cm length of $\approx$ 3 cm high -

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Retaining wall visible in room 4 and 5.
Robbed on its eastern part. Obviously room 4 has been more exposed to robbing than room 5.

Few Inclusions $\rightarrow$ pottery, tiles + Tufo slag (medium size)

Ashlar blocks standing on bedrock (covered by a fine sandy layer of soil)

No binding Agent $\rightarrow$ presence of sandy soil

Ashlar blocks show traces of cutting (horizontal) $\rightarrow$ According to Jeff, just traces due to the poor quality of tufo.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by IBRGANE

on 29.07.10

Revised by CPM

on 29.07.10

PDFd by

on

Entered by

on